

Additional Materials for Leveling Up: Experiences and Evidence-driven Upgrades to a Game Coding Camp for Autistic High School Students

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What is Discord?

Discord is a free voice, video, and text chatting app where users can join and create “servers” to chat with others in communities with specific interests. Discord is available in a web browser or as an app on PCs (Windows, Mac, and Linux), smartphones, and on gaming consoles. Discord can be downloaded at <https://discord.com/>.

Creating a Discord Account

To properly use Discord, you’ll need to create an account. Generally, this involves picking a username, if your intentions are to be involved in public discord servers, then you might want to choose an anonymous username instead of something like `firstnamelastinitial` or `firstnamelastnamebirthyear`. Discord will walk you through the account creation process.

Creating a Discord Server

1. Click on the large plus icon in the left sidebar to create a new server.
2. You can either create a server from a template (e.g. Gaming, Friends, Study Group, Club, etc.) or select “Create My Own.”
3. You’ll define your server more in-depth by selecting the server name and a server icon before creating the server.
4. After server creation, you’ll be able to customize the channels within your server. You can have as many channels or as few as you would like. You can set a channel name and give a description of what the channel is to be used for in the channel description. The different types of channels include:
 - (a) Text – textual chats where members can chat with other members
 - (b) Voice/Video – voice chats where members can share their screens, themselves (like in a video call), and talk to one another
5. Lastly, you can invite other people to your server. You can click the “Invite to Server” button to either search for your friends on Discord or send an invite link.

Setting up User Roles & Permissions

For our camp discord server, we used user roles as a way to restrict which users were able to access which channels. We had two groups of channels, those for our Instructors and those for our Campers. For example, everyone with the “Instructor” role was able to see all of the channels for both those with the “Instructor” and “Camper” roles. Those with just the “Camper” role were unable to see the channels for the “Instructor” role. Read more about managing role and channel permissions at <https://support.discord.com/hc/en-us/articles/214836687-Discord-Roles-and-Permissions>.

Server Moderation & Discord AutoMod

Discord provides servers with a bunch of tools and resources for moderating Discord servers. You can find the full Safety and Moderation Resources at <https://discord.com/community-moderation-safety>. Additionally, there's an entire library about being safe on Discord, with resources for parents and educators at <https://discord.com/safety-library>.

For our camps, the instructors were also tasked with moderating the Discord server. We used tools such as slowmode (to slow the chat down to 1 message sent by a user every 20 seconds for better moderation) and Discord's AutoMod to help flag any messages that weren't family-friendly. We found a list of commonly blocked words and added it to AutoMod's "Block Custom Words" filter, which flagged messages that included those specific words.

Custom Discord Bots

We incorporated a custom Discord Bot into our camp to send regular reminders to campers and automate daily tasks to relieve some stress off of the instructor team. Our Discord bot code can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17955400>.

Additional moderation features can be created using Custom Discord Bots. These are programs that you create and host yourself (for example, we used Python to create our bot and Amazon Web Services to continually host our bot) that can do very specific tasks. For example, the Discord bot we used in our 2024 camp sent a message every morning reminding campers that camp started in 20 minutes. More information about building a custom discord bot can be found at <https://discord.com/developers/docs/intro>.

There are also custom Discord bots created by other people that you can invite to your server. MEE6 is a popular bot that you can customize to fit your server's theme and add moderation features to.